

Wet Vibration Analysis and Uncertainty Quantification of Ship Plates

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Abstract. Vibration of plate structures in air (dry) and in contact with fluid (wet) are of great interest and practical importance in naval architecture and marine applications. Therefore, a fundamental understanding of the natural vibration frequency and mode of various plate structures under different boundary conditions and environments is essential, especially for early-stage ship structural designs. In this paper, the dry and wet vibrations of simply supported rectangular Mindlin plates is studied with emphases on developing closed-form solutions of vibration frequencies and quantification of uncertainties of different types. In fluid-structure interaction modeling, potential flow assumption is adopted for the fluid while orthotropic thick-plate condition is used for starting the plate bending formulation. The coupling between the fluid and plate is achieved through the fluid-plate interface, where the pressure is the same across the fluid-plate interfaces and the fluid-plate contact is permanent. Closed-form analytical solutions of added mass due to hydrodynamic effects of the potential fluid with several typical boundary conditions are presented first, and then the differential governing equations of orthotropic Mindlin plate with added mass considered are derived for the first time. Subsequently, simple solutions of wet vibration frequency are presented for both Mindlin plate and Kirchhoff-Love plate. With the derived closed-form solutions, parametric study and comparison between these two plate models can be easily conducted. For a given fluid-plate interaction model, the variations of the obtained vibration frequency are further evaluated with probabilistic analysis and Monte-Carlo simulation by considering the uncertainties and variations of the influencing parameters. This study sheds significant light on the fundamental fluid-structure interaction in terms of wet vibration and provides potential opportunities for further development in ship structural reliability, noise and comfort management, and the control of acoustic signatures.

Keywords: *Natural frequency, dry/wet vibration, rectangular plate, potential flow, uncertainty quantification, Monte-Carlo simulation.*

1 Introduction

Analyzing dry/wet vibration frequencies/modes and avoiding resonance are required for the design of naval structures. Forced vibration and resonance excited by a spectrum of vibration resources, such as engines, propellers, slamming, springing, main machinery/shafting system, and others, are the main vibration issues [1-4]. Excessive ship vibration may result in fatigue failure of local structural members, malfunction of machinery, equipment, sensors, modern monitoring apparatus, and issues related to passenger comfort, crew habitability and safety. Additionally, vibration is a key factor in detecting or reducing acoustic signatures of surface ships, submarines, and other manned and autonomous naval vessels. Therefore, understanding the fundamental fluid-structure interaction mechanisms in terms of vibration is critical for many important naval applications. Vibrating structures in contact with fluids result in complex fluid motion and equivalent added mass, which can be large enough to significantly decrease the frequency of vibration and change the vibration modes from the dry condition. Analytical and numerical methods are often used in ship structural vibration analysis, with the former providing valuable physical insights while the latter providing substantial details. It should be noted that local structural resonances are often considered to be minor problems, as the corrective approach of local stiffening may be easily achievable [3]. However, as modern ship structures are getting more complex and the increasing demands for more effective design and building processes, fundamental understanding of ship structural vibration is still greatly in demand.

As the fundamental structural elements, plates with a wide range of span/thickness ratios are commonly used in naval architecture and marine engineering. Rectangular plate represents several different kinds of panels for ship construction, such as plate panels, stiffener panels, and girder panels. The published papers and reports on the

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vibration of rectangular plates are abundant, and most of them are on isotropic thin plates, which can be described by the classical (Kirchhoff-Love) plate theory (CPT) [5]. For example, dry free vibration and elastic deflections/stresses of plates under various boundary and loading conditions for naval and marine applications have been studied by Smith [6] and Madsen [7] with CPT for thin orthotropic plates. However, the effects of rotatory inertia and shear deformation, both of which reduce the natural frequencies of thick plates, are neglected in CPT. Reissner [8] and Mindlin [9-11] developed first-order plate theories for isotropic plates by considering these effects. Liew [12] used two-dimensional polynomials as the admissible functions for Mindlin plates and systematically conducted numerical simulations with the Rayleigh-Ritz method. In a series of papers [13-18], the isotropic Mindlin plate theory has been applied to a wide variety of naval and marine structural applications including free and forced vibrations of complex structures with openings and added stiffeners. Shahrokh and Arsanjani [19] derived the exact characteristic equations for free vibration of a rectangular Mindlin plate with several typical boundary conditions. Similar exact closed-form solutions have also been obtained for free vibrations of orthotropic rectangular Mindlin plates by using the separation of variables [20]. Papkov and Banerjee [21] investigated the free vibration of orthotropic Mindlin plates in the context of dynamic stiffness formulation. Levinson [22] and Reddy [23, 24] proposed third-order shear deformation theories that ensure zero shear stress/strain at the free surfaces of plates and derived the governing equations respectively with the equilibrium method and variational approach.

The presence of fluid can significantly affect the vibration of a plate when it is in contact with fluid, either floating or submerged. With Rayleigh's approach, Lamb [25] calculated the natural frequencies of a thin clamped circular plate in an aperture of an infinite rigid plane wall coupled with water based on the assumption that wet vibration mode shapes are the same as those in vacuum. Kwak [26] calculated added virtual mass (AVM) of rectangular plates with Ritz method. The ratio between the kinetic energy of the fluid and the kinetic energy of the structure is often referred to as the added virtual mass incremental (AVMI) factor [27, 28]. All these solutions are approximate in nature due to the hypothesis that dry and wet vibration modes are equal, but the natural frequencies can be easily obtained by using the non-dimensional AVMI and the modal properties of plates in dry vibration. The wet vibration of isotropic Mindlin plates in contact with fluids has been studied for various naval and marine structures [29-32] with virtual energy principles and numerical methods. As an alternative approach, the velocity potential function of fluid and Bernoulli's equation have been employed to obtain the fluid pressure applied on the free surface of plates [33-34]. With this approach, the previous assumptions that the wet and dry vibration mode shapes are the same [25-28] can be abandoned and the free vibration analysis of moderately thick isotropic rectangular plates, immersed in fluid or floating on fluid surface, has been studied [35]. Closed-form characteristic equations have been derived for the plates under six different boundary conditions [35].

It should be noted that there are many plate theories with different levels of accuracy and complexity [36-40]. Different models lead to different results, and the model uncertainty is a major part of total uncertainties in the predicted results. For a given plate vibration model, the uncertainties or variations in the basic variables of a plate structure can also greatly impact the overall reliability of the assessed vibration performance. Specifically, the actual values of these variables are often different from the nominal or design values, and these actual values tend to behave in a random manner [41]. Structural reliability-based methodologies with probabilistic characterization capabilities are required to understand the impact of the variations and uncertainties on the overall performance. Random behaviors of the basic variables can cause the predicted properties of structures to vary in a range that can lead to overprediction or underprediction [41]. Understanding and quantifying the randomness and uncertainty characteristics of these variables allows the researchers to better understand the prediction/test results, and it can also help the designers to account for the variations in the design of marine structures.

In this paper, the dry and wet vibration analysis of rectangular plates with the classical Kirchhoff-Love plate theory and Mindlin plate theory is conducted with the following aims: (1) develop closed-form solutions for wet vibration of simply supported rectangular plates so that insights can be gained from the mathematical structures and the analytical results, (2) evaluate the differences between the classical Kirchhoff-Love plate theory and Mindlin plate theory, and examine the implications and applications of these models in marine structural designs, and (3) compare the contributions of the uncertainties of the relevant parameters to the variations of the predicted vibration frequency values. This paper is planned as follows: the formulation of potential fluid flow is described first, followed by the development of bending governing equations of Mindlin rectangular plates. The uncertainties and variations of key parameters in ship structures are subsequently reviewed and a Monte-Carlo simulation method is introduced for uncertainty quantification of random events. The major observations made from this dry and wet vibration study are provided subsequently, and finally the conclusions and future research needs are provided at the end of this paper.

2 Fluid formation

2.1 Potential flow

A rectangular plate with fluid potentially on both lower and upper sides is schematically shown in Fig.1. The plate is oriented in such a way that its undeformed middle surface contains x and y axes of a right-handed rectangular Cartesian coordinate system (x, y, z) . The center of the coordinate is located at a corner of the middle surface of the plate. a, b , and h are respectively the length, width, and thickness of the plate. p_l and p_u are respectively the pressures exerted on the lower (i.e. $z = -h/2$) and upper (i.e. $z = h/2$) surfaces of the plate.

Figure 1. Schematic of the coordinate, dimensions, and loading conditions of a plate

The presence of fluid on the top or/and bottom surfaces impacts the natural frequencies, vibration modes, and other dynamic characteristics of the plate. The following assumptions are made to model the dynamic behaviors of the fluid flowing around the plate.

- (1) the amplitude of the vibrations is small for both plates and the surrounding fluid
- (2) ideal potential flow meaning the fluid is homogeneous, incompressible, inviscid, and irrotational
- (3) no separation or cavitation at the fluid-plate interfaces
- (4) the pressure exerted from the fluid on the plate is normal to the plate surfaces, and there is no shear stress or strain at the fluid-plate interfaces
- (5) zero velocity normal to the rigid walls, and no wave on the free surfaces of the fluid domain.

Based on these assumptions, the fluid can be fully described with a velocity potential function ϕ , which must satisfy the Laplace equation throughout the fluid domain, Eq. (1) [33-35].

$$\nabla^2 \phi = \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial z^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

To solve Eq. (1), the velocity potential function ϕ can be further expressed in Eq. (2) through separation of variables.

$$\phi(x, y, z, t) = F(z)S(x, y, t) \quad (2)$$

where $F(z)$ and $S(x, y, t)$ are two independent functions, which will be determined from fluid boundary conditions.

Based on Bernoulli's equation, the fluid pressure on the upper and lower surfaces of the plate can be expressed in Eq. (3)

$$p_u = p_u \Big|_{z = \frac{h}{2}} = -\rho_f \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} \Big|_{z = \frac{h}{2}} \quad (3-1)$$

$$p_l = p_l \Big|_{z = -\frac{h}{2}} = -\rho_f \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} \Big|_{z = -\frac{h}{2}} \quad (3-2)$$

where ρ_f is the density of the fluid with the unit of mass per unit volume.

The impermeability of the plate and no-separation conditions at the fluid-plate interfaces require that the out-of-plane velocity component of the fluid on the fluid-plate interfaces match the instantaneous change rate of the

plate deflection, w , in the transverse direction, Eq. (4). This condition implies permanent contact between the plate surfaces and the fluid in contact.

$$\left. \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z} \right|_{z = \frac{h}{2}} = \left. \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \right|_{z = \frac{h}{2}} \quad (4-1)$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z} \right|_{z = -\frac{h}{2}} = \left. \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \right|_{z = -\frac{h}{2}} \quad (4-2)$$

By combining Eq. (2) and Eq. (4), Eq. (5) and Eq. (6) can be obtained.

$$S(x, y, t) = \frac{1}{\left. \frac{dF(z)}{dz} \right|_{z = \frac{h}{2}}} \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \quad (5-1)$$

$$S(x, y, t) = \frac{1}{\left. \frac{dF(z)}{dz} \right|_{z = -\frac{h}{2}}} \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \quad (5-2)$$

$$\phi(x, y, z, t) = \frac{F(z)}{\left. \frac{dF(z)}{dz} \right|_{z = \frac{h}{2}}} \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \quad (6-1)$$

$$\phi(x, y, z, t) = \frac{F(z)}{\left. \frac{dF}{dz} \right|_{z = -\frac{h}{2}}} \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \quad (6-2)$$

Eq. (6-1) and Eq. (6-2) respectively represent the velocity potential in terms of lateral deflection, w , of the plate at upper and lower plate surfaces.

Substituting Eq. (6) into Eq. (1) leads to Eq. (7) through Eq. (9).

$$\nabla^2 \phi = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \right) F(z) + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \right) F(z) + \frac{d^2 F(z)}{dz^2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \right) = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{d^2 F(z)}{dz^2} - \mu_f^2 F(z) = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\mu_f^2 = - \frac{\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \right) + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \right)}{\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \right)} \quad (9)$$

where μ_f is a plane wave number and it is a real constant. For simply supported boundary condition, the lateral deflection $w(x, y, t)$ of the plate corresponding to a set of wave numbers (m, n) can be expressed in Eq. (10) with separation of spatial and temporal variables. $T(t)$ can be an arbitrary time-dependent function.

$$w_{mn}(x, y, t) = \sin\left(\frac{m\pi x}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{n\pi y}{b}\right) T(t) \quad (10)$$

Substituting Eq. (10) into Eq. (9) leads to Eq. (11)

$$\mu_f = \pi \sqrt{\left(\frac{m}{a}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{n}{b}\right)^2} \quad (11)$$

μ_f generally varies with boundary condition, but the difference is insignificant, and it can be assumed to be independent of boundary condition in many applications [33,35]. The general solution of Eq. (8) can be expressed in Eq. (12).

$$F(z) = A_1 e^{\mu_f z} + A_2 e^{-\mu_f z} \quad (12)$$

where A_1 and A_2 are constants, which can be determined by applying boundary conditions for a given specific problem. By substituting Eq. (12) into Eq. (2), the final velocity potential function can be obtained, Eq. (13).

$$\phi(x, y, z, t) = \frac{A_1 e^{\mu_f z} + A_2 e^{-\mu_f z}}{\mu_f \left(A_1 e^{\mu_f \frac{h}{2}} - A_2 e^{-\mu_f \frac{h}{2}} \right)} \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \quad \left(z \geq \frac{h}{2} \right) \quad (13-1)$$

$$\phi(x, y, z, t) = \frac{A_1 e^{\mu_f z} + A_2 e^{-\mu_f z}}{\mu_f \left(A_1 e^{-\mu_f \frac{h}{2}} - A_2 e^{\mu_f \frac{h}{2}} \right)} \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \quad \left(z \leq -\frac{h}{2} \right) \quad (13-2)$$

2.2 Typical fluid-plate boundary conditions

Three typical fluid-plate boundary conditions are considered here to illustrate how to apply Eq. (13) to specific problems: (1) fluid-plate with a free fluid surface, (2) floating plate with a rigid wall, (3) submerged plate.

2.2.1 Fluid-plate model with free surface

Fig.2 (a) schematically illustrates this scenario, which can be used to model the bulging vibration of the bottom plate of a tanker filled with fluid. The linearized free surface boundary condition holds when the surface perturbations are negligible, and $\phi(x, y, z) = \bar{\phi}(x, y, z) e^{i\omega t}$. $\bar{\phi}$ is the amplitude of the velocity potential parameter and the overbar can be dropped for clarity. Therefore, Eq. (14) can be obtained [33, 35].

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z} \Big|_{z = h_1 + \frac{h}{2}} = -\frac{1}{g} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial t^2} \Big|_{z = h_1 + \frac{h}{2}} = -\frac{\omega^2}{g} \phi \Big|_{z = h_1 + \frac{h}{2}} \quad (14)$$

where g is acceleration due to gravity, ω is the angular frequency of the wave motion caused by the vibration of the plate. Substituting Eq. (13-1) into Eq. (14), the potential function of the fluid is obtained, Eq. (15).

$$\phi(x, y, z, t) = \frac{e^{\mu_f z} + c_1 e^{\mu_f(2h_1+h-z)}}{\mu_f \left[e^{\mu_f \frac{h}{2}} - c_1 e^{\mu_f(2h_1+\frac{h}{2})} \right]} \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \quad (15)$$

where $c_1 = \frac{\mu_f g - \omega^2}{\mu_f g + \omega^2}$, c_1 is a function of frequency but can be approximately set as $c_1 = -1$ [33]. This approximation can be made to avoid handling non-linear eigenvalue problems [33].

The fluid pressure exerted on the upper surface of the plate, Eq. (16), is obtained by substituting Eq. (15) into Eq. (3-1).

$$\Delta p = p_u - p_l = m_{add}^* \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} = -\frac{\rho_f}{\mu_f} \left(\frac{1 + c_1 e^{2\mu_f h_1}}{1 - c_1 e^{2\mu_f h_1}} \right) \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} \quad (16)$$

where $m_{add}^* = -\frac{\rho_f}{\mu_f} \left(\frac{1 + c_1 e^{2\mu_f h_1}}{1 - c_1 e^{2\mu_f h_1}} \right)$ is added mass caused by the net fluid pressure. For this scenario, $p_l = 0$ at the free lower surface of the plate. Eq. (16) can be combined with the plate bending equation to derive the solutions of wet vibration.

2.2.2 Floating plate bounded by a rigid wall

Fig.2 (b) schematically illustrates this scenario, where a plate is floating on the top surface of the fluid, which is bounded by a rigid wall at the bottom. Eq. (17) is satisfied at the rigid wall.

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z} \Big|_{z = -h_2} = 0 \quad (17)$$

By introducing Eq. (13-2) into Eq. (17), the velocity potential, Eq. (18), can be derived.

$$\phi(x, y, z, t) = \frac{e^{\mu_f z} + C_2 e^{-\mu_f z}}{\mu_f \left[e^{-\mu_f \frac{h}{2}} - C_2 e^{\mu_f \frac{h}{2}} \right]} \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \quad (18)$$

where $C_2 = e^{-2\mu_f h_2}$

The net dynamic pressure for this scenario can then be determined, Eq. (19).

$$\Delta p = p_u - p_l = m_{add}^* \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\rho_f}{\mu_f} \left(\frac{1 + C_2 e^{2\mu_f h}}{1 - C_2 e^{2\mu_f h}} \right) \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} \quad (19)$$

where $m_{add}^* = \frac{\rho_f}{\mu_f} \left(\frac{1 + C_2 e^{2\mu_f h}}{1 - C_2 e^{2\mu_f h}} \right)$ is the added mass caused by the movement of the fluid. For a plate floating on the surface of the fluid, $p_u = 0$.

2.2.3 Submerged plate bounded by a rigid wall

In case of a submerged plate, Fig.2 (c), the total net dynamic pressure, Eq. (20), is superposition of the pressures at the top and the bottom surfaces of the plate.

$$\Delta p = m_{add}^* \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} = -\frac{\rho_f}{\mu_f} \left[\left(\frac{1 + C_1 e^{2\mu_f h_1}}{1 - C_1 e^{2\mu_f h_1}} \right) - \left(\frac{1 + C_2 e^{2\mu_f h}}{1 - C_2 e^{2\mu_f h}} \right) \right] \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} \quad (20)$$

Figure 2. Schematic of fluid-plate interactions: (a) fluid-plate with a free surface, (b) floating plate, (c) submerged plate

3 Dry and wet vibrations of rectangular plates

Without loss of generality, let's consider a thick orthotropic rectangular plate of length a , width b , and uniform thickness h , as shown in Fig.1. Based on the assumptions of Mindlin plate theory, both normal stress and normal strain are ignored, i.e., $\sigma_{zz} = 0$ and $\varepsilon_{zz} = \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} = 0$. Additionally, planes remain planes before and after deformation. There are three fundamental variables in the Mindlin plate theory (MPT): ψ_x , ψ_y , and w . ψ_x and ψ_y are

respectively the angles of rotation of normal lines around the neutral axes due to plate bending respectively with respect to y and x , and w is transverse deflection in z direction.

The differential governing equations of plate vibration with the presence of external loads or pressures for an orthotropic Mindlin plate can be expressed in Eq. (21).

$$\frac{\partial M_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial y} - Q_x = -\rho J \frac{\partial^2 \psi_x}{\partial t^2} \quad (21-1)$$

$$\frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial M_y}{\partial y} - Q_y = -\rho J \frac{\partial^2 \psi_y}{\partial t^2} \quad (21-2)$$

$$\frac{\partial Q_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Q_y}{\partial y} - \Delta p(x, y, t) = \rho_p h \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} = (\rho_p h + m_{add}^*) \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} \quad (21-3)$$

where M_x , M_y , and M_{xy} are bending moments per length. Q_x and Q_y are shear forces per length. $J = \frac{h^3}{12}$ is line moment of inertia, and ρ is the mass density per volume. $\Delta p(x, y, t) = p_u(x, y, t) - p_l(x, y, t)$ is the net distributed load per area (pressure), with positive Δp pointing to the negative z direction. $p_u(x, y, t)$ and $p_l(x, y, t)$ are respectively the pressures applied to the upper and lower surfaces of the plate. Since the dynamic pressure of the fluid is perpendicular to the plate surfaces, Eq. (22) can be obtained based on dynamic equilibrium analysis.

$$\Delta p(x, y, t) = m_{add}^* \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} \quad (22)$$

where m_{add}^* can be treated as the equivalent mass per unit area $dA = dx dy$ added to the plate from the surrounding moving fluids, and it is dependent on fluid modeling and fluid-plate conditions, as shown in Eq. (16), Eq. (19), and Eq. (20).

The relationships between the stress resultants M_x , M_y , M_{xy} , Q_x , and Q_y and the generalized displacements ψ_x , ψ_y , and w of the orthotropic Mindlin plate are expressed in Eq. (23).

$$M_x = - \left(D_{11} \frac{\partial \psi_x}{\partial x} + D_{12} \frac{\partial \psi_y}{\partial y} \right) \quad (23-1)$$

$$M_y = - \left(D_{22} \frac{\partial \psi_y}{\partial y} + D_{21} \frac{\partial \psi_x}{\partial x} \right) \quad (23-2)$$

$$M_{xy} = -D_{66} \left(\frac{\partial \psi_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \psi_y}{\partial x} \right) \quad (23-3)$$

$$Q_x = C_{55} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} - \psi_x \right) \quad (23-4)$$

$$Q_y = C_{44} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} - \psi_y \right) \quad (23-5)$$

where the bending and shear rigidities are:

$$D_{11} = \frac{E_1 h^3}{12(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21})}$$

$$D_{22} = \frac{E_2 h^3}{12(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21})}$$

$$D_{12} = \frac{\nu_{21} E_1 h^3}{12(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21})} = D_{21} = \frac{\nu_{12} E_2 h^3}{12(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21})}, \quad D_{66} = \frac{G_{12} h^3}{12}, \quad C_{44} = k' G_{23} h, \quad C_{55} = k' G_{13} h$$

It is assumed in Eq. (23) that the principal directions X , Y , and Z of the orthotropic plate coincide with the coordinate x , y , and z . Specifically, E_1 and E_2 are respectively the Young's moduli in the major principal X and minor principal Y directions; G_{12} , G_{13} and G_{23} are respectively the shear moduli in XY , XZ and YZ planes; ν_{12} and ν_{21} are the major and minor Poisson's ratios, respectively. Based on Maxwell-Betti reciprocal theorem, the following relation holds: $\nu_{12} E_2 = \nu_{21} E_1$. Unlike the isotropic materials, the three shear modulus parameters cannot be derived purely from Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios, and must be experimentally determined. k' is the empirical transverse shear correction coefficient, applied to the transverse shear forces because the transverse shear strains have a nonlinear dependency on the thickness coordinate.

For harmonic oscillation, rotational angles and transverse deflection can be expressed in Eq. (24).

$$\psi_x(x, y, t) = \bar{\psi}_x(x, y)e^{i\omega t} \quad (24 - 1)$$

$$\psi_y(x, y, t) = \bar{\psi}_y(x, y)e^{i\omega t} \quad (24 - 2)$$

$$w(x, y, t) = \bar{w}(x, y)e^{i\omega t} \quad (24 - 3)$$

$\bar{\psi}_x$, $\bar{\psi}_y$ and \bar{w} are amplitudes of the corresponding parameters. For clarity and simplicity, the overbar is dropped in the following equations. By substituting Eq. (24) into Eq. (21), the new governing equations, Eq. (25), can be obtained.

$$D_1 \frac{\partial^2 \psi_x}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_x}{\partial y^2} + D_3 \frac{\partial^2 \psi_y}{\partial x \partial y} + C_1 \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} - \psi_x \right) + \gamma^4 \psi_x = 0 \quad (25 - 1)$$

$$D_2 \frac{\partial^2 \psi_y}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_y}{\partial x^2} + D_3 \frac{\partial^2 \psi_x}{\partial x \partial y} + C_2 \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} - \psi_y \right) + \gamma^4 \psi_y = 0 \quad (25 - 2)$$

$$C_1 \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial \psi_x}{\partial x} \right) + C_2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\partial \psi_y}{\partial y} \right) + \beta^4 w = 0 \quad (25 - 3)$$

where

$$D_1 = \frac{D_{11}}{D_{66}}, D_2 = \frac{D_{22}}{D_{66}}, D_3 = \frac{D_{12} + D_{66}}{D_{66}}, C_1 = \frac{C_{55}}{D_{66}}, C_2 = \frac{C_{44}}{D_{66}}$$

$$\gamma^4 = \frac{\rho_p J \omega^2}{D_{66}}, \beta^4 = \frac{(\rho_p h + m_{add}^*) \omega^2}{D_{66}}$$

Liu and Xing [20] derived the closed-form solutions of the free vibrations of rectangular orthotropic Mindlin plates under several typical boundary conditions including simply supported boundary condition. By the same token, closed-form analytical solutions to the wet vibration of orthotropic rectangular Mindlin plates can be obtained for the same typical boundary conditions by following the same established procedures [20]. For simplicity and clarity, only isotropic Mindlin plate under simply supported boundary condition is considered in the rest of the paper to demonstrate the basic solution seeking procedure. The only difference between the dry vibration [20] and wet vibration shown here is the presence of m_{add}^* while the solution structures for both are the same. Two degenerative forms of Mindlin plate theory are also considered in the following sections for comparison purposes. Specifically, after eliminating ψ_x and ψ_y in Eq. (25), a single governing equation, Eq. (26), for isotropic Mindlin plate can be derived [42].

$$\left(\nabla^2 - \frac{\rho_p}{k'G} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \right) \left(D \nabla^2 - \frac{\rho_p h^3}{12} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \right) w + \rho_p h \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} + \left(1 - \frac{D}{k'Gh} \nabla^2 + \frac{\rho_p h^2}{12k'G} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \right) \Delta p = 0 \quad (26)$$

where $\nabla^2 w = \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2}$, $\nabla^4 w = \left(\frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + 2 \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial y^4} \right)$, $D = \frac{Eh^3}{12(1-\nu^2)}$, and $\Delta p = p_u - p_l$.

If the rotatory inertia related items ($z - t$ coupled) are omitted, Eq. (26) can be reduced to Eq. (27).

$$D \left(\nabla^2 - \frac{\rho_p}{k'G} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \right) \nabla^2 w + \rho_p h \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} + \left(1 - \frac{D}{k'Gh} \nabla^2 \right) \Delta p = 0 \quad (27)$$

If the transverse shear deformation related items ($k'G$) are neglected, Eq. (26) can be reduced to Eq. (28).

$$\left(D \nabla^2 - \frac{\rho_p h^3}{12} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \right) \nabla^2 w + \rho_p h \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} + \Delta p = 0 \quad (28)$$

If both rotatory inertia and transverse shear deformation related terms are omitted in Eq. (26), the classical Kirchhoff-Love plate theory can be obtained, Eq. (29).

$$D\nabla^4 w + \rho_p h \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} + \Delta p = 0 \quad (29)$$

For simply supported boundary condition: $w = w'' = 0$ at $x = 0, a$ and $y = 0, b$, the frequency or characteristic equation of Eq. (26) is now Eq. (30).

$$D \left[\left(\frac{m\pi}{a} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{n\pi}{b} \right)^2 \right]^2 - \rho_p \left\{ \left[\frac{D}{k'G} \left(1 + \frac{m_{add}^*}{\rho h} \right) + \frac{h^3}{12} \right] \left[\left(\frac{m\pi}{a} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{n\pi}{b} \right)^2 \right] + h \left(1 + \frac{m_{add}^*}{\rho h} \right) \right\} \omega_{mn}^2 + \left[\frac{\rho_p^2 h^3}{12k'G} \left(1 + \frac{m_{add}^*}{\rho h} \right) \right] \omega_{mn}^4 = 0 \quad (30)$$

The solution of Eq. (30) can be expressed in Eq. (31).

$$(\omega_{mn})^2 = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a} \quad (31)$$

where

$$a = \frac{\rho_p^2 h^3}{12k'G} (1 + \bar{m}_{add}^*)$$

$$b = -\rho_p \left\{ \left[\frac{D}{k'G} (1 + \bar{m}_{add}^*) + \frac{h^3}{12} \right] \left[\left(\frac{m\pi}{a} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{n\pi}{b} \right)^2 \right] + h(1 + \bar{m}_{add}^*) \right\}$$

$$c = D \left[\left(\frac{m\pi}{a} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{n\pi}{b} \right)^2 \right]^2$$

$\omega_{mn} = 2\pi f_{mn}$ is circular frequency corresponding to (m, n) mode; m and n are respectively the numbers of half-waves in x and y directions; f_{mn} represents ordinary natural frequency, and nondimensional mass is $\bar{m}_{add}^* = \frac{m_{add}^*}{\rho_p h}$.

The frequency of the classical plate theory can be simplified to Eq. (32) by neglecting both the rotatory inertia and shear deformation related terms in Eq. (30).

$$\omega_{mn} = \left[\left(\frac{m\pi}{a} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{n\pi}{b} \right)^2 \right] \sqrt{\frac{D}{\rho_p h (1 + \bar{m}_{add}^*)}} \quad (32)$$

Eq. (30) and Eq. (32) are wet vibration solutions obtained by coupling plate vibration with fluid movement through Δp or \bar{m}_{add}^* . Dry vibration or free vibration of the plate in air or vacuum can be realized by setting $\Delta p = 0$. The added mass formulae under the three typical boundary conditions are provided in Eq. (16), Eq. (19), and Eq. (20), respectively. From Eq. (32) the ratio of wet vibration and dry vibration in terms of frequency can be expressed in Eq. (33).

$$\frac{\omega_{fluid}}{\omega_{air}} = \frac{f_{fluid}}{f_{air}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \bar{m}_{add}^*}} \quad (33)$$

It should be noted that Lamb's energy approach on wet vibration of clamped circular plates [25], Kawk's energy approach [26], and similar works [27, 28] on wet vibration of rectangular plates resulted in Eq. (34).

$$\frac{f_{fluid}}{f_{air}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \beta}} \quad (34)$$

where $\beta = \Gamma \frac{\rho_f a}{\rho_p h}$ is added virtual mass incremental (AVMI) factor and Γ is the non-dimensional added virtual mass incremental (NAVMI) factor. a is the radius of the circular plate or length of the rectangular plate. h is the thickness of the plate. It is interesting to note that both the equilibrium approach and energy approach lead to similar formulas. However, the assumptions made in deriving Eq. (34) is: dry and wet vibrations have the same vibration modes. By contrast, there is no such limitation for deriving Eq. (33).

4 Uncertainty analysis of ship structures

Based on literature review, Hess et al. [41] compiled statistical information and data on both strength and load random variables for quantifying the probabilistic characteristics of these variables which are needed for reliability analysis and design of ship structures. For a given vibration model and boundary condition, it can be seen from the plate vibration equations that the vibration relevant factors include plate thickness h , length a , width b , Young's modulus (modulus of elasticity) of the plate E , Poisson's ratio ν , density of the plate ρ_p , density of fluid (water) ρ_f , and some environmental parameters. The variables, probabilistic distribution function (PSD), and the values of the distribution parameters for vibration evaluation are summarized in Table 1. Lognormal probabilistic distribution is recommended for describing the thickness and length of the ship plates, and normal probabilistic distribution is found to be the best to describe the width of the plates and Young's modulus [41]. For a given parameter X , the mean, μ_X , coefficient of variation (COV), and standard deviation (STD) s_X can be simply calculated with s_X/μ_X and are listed in the last column of Table 1.

Table 1 Recommended probabilistic characteristics of basic random variables [41]

Variable	Distribution type	Mean, μ_X or/and $\mu_{\ln(X)}$ (measured/nominal)	COV	STD, s_X or/and $s_{\ln(X)}$ (measured/nominal)
Thickness of plate, h	Lognormal	h : 1.05 $\ln(h)$: 0.048	0.044	h : 0.046 $\ln(h)$: 0.044
Length of plate, a	Lognormal	a : 0.998 $\ln(a)$: -0.0031	0.046	0.046 $\ln(a)$: 0.046
Width of plate, b	Normal	0.992	0.028	0.028
Young's modulus, E	Normal	0.987	0.076	0.075
Poisson's ratio, ν	Deterministic	1	0	0
Density of plate, ρ_p	Deterministic	1	0	0
Density of fluid, ρ_f	Deterministic	1	0	0

Lognormally distributed X and the normally distributed $\ln(X)$ have different means and standard deviations. Specifically, μ_X and s_X are respectively the mean and standard deviation of the distribution of X ; $\mu_{\ln(X)}$, and $s_{\ln(X)}$ are respectively the mean and the standard deviation of the lognormal distribution with variable $\ln(X)$. The relationships between these two sets of parameters are shown in Eq. (35). In practice, it is usually more convenient to convert a lognormal distribution to a normal distribution first by taking advantage of the properties of normal distribution. The obtained results can then be converted to the original lognormal distribution for results interpretation.

$$\mu_{\ln(X)} = \ln\left(\frac{\mu_X^2}{\sqrt{\mu_X^2 + s_X^2}}\right), \quad (35 - 1)$$

$$s_{\ln(X)} = \sqrt{\ln\left(1 + \frac{s_X^2}{\mu_X^2}\right)} \quad (35 - 2)$$

$$\mu_X = \exp\left(\mu_{\ln(X)} + \frac{s_{\ln(X)}^2}{2}\right) \quad (35 - 3)$$

$$s_X = \sqrt{[\exp(s_{\ln(X)}^2) - 1]\exp(2\mu_{\ln(X)} + s_{\ln(X)}^2)} \quad (35 - 4)$$

For complex probabilistic problems with multiple variables, for which closed-form solutions are not available or difficult to obtain, the Monte Carlo simulation method is a convenient and accurate tool to find approximate solutions. Box-Muller transform, Eq. (36), is often used to generate a pair of independent standard normally distributed random numbers with zero expectations and unit variances. The sampling process is to generate samples from the uniform distribution on the interval $[0,1]$ and map them to standard normally distributed samples. Mathematically, supposed U_1 and U_2 are two sets of independent samples chosen from the uniform distribution on the unit interval $[0,1]$, and define two independent variables Z_1 and Z_2 , Eq. (36).

$$Z_1 = \sqrt{-2\ln U_1} \cos(2\pi U_2) \quad (36 - 1)$$

$$Z_2 = \sqrt{-2\ln U_1} \sin(2\pi U_2) \quad (36 - 2)$$

With Eq. (36), Z_1 and Z_2 are independent random variables with the standard normal distribution. The distribution of variable X can be calculated for a given set of μ_X and s_X : $X = \mu_X + Zs_X$. For a lognormal distribution function, the relationship is still valid, with $\ln(X)$, $\mu_{\ln(X)}$, and $s_{\ln(X)}$ replacing X , μ_X , and s_X .

It should be noted that caution must be taken when using the values of probabilistic parameters in Table 1 in reliability assessment and reliability-based design of ship structures because these results can be revised as new data and research on the subject emerge [41]. Additionally, these results might not be appropriate for special situations where thorough and rigorous analyses are required, because they represent only the ranges and the weighted averages of the statistical values collected [41].

5 Results and discussion

5.1 Added mass due to wet vibration

Fig.3 (a), (b), and (c) respectively show the nondimensional added mass, i.e. $\bar{m}_{add}^* = \frac{m_{add}^*}{\rho_p h}$, for the three fluid-plate interaction systems: (a) fluid-plate with free surface, (b) floating plate, (c) submerged plate, with Eq. (16), Eq. (19), and Eq. (20), respectively. In plotting Fig.3, the density of sea water $\rho_f = 1025 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and the density of steel plate $\rho_p = 7850 \text{ kg/m}^3$ are used, therefore, $\bar{\rho} = \rho_f/\rho_p = 0.1306$. In Fig.3, only squared plates, i.e., $a = b$, and three symmetrical wave numbers ($m = n=1, 3, 10$) are considered for illustration purposes. Additionally, $h_1 = h_2 = a$ is used in all cases. The ratio of plate thickness and plate length $h/a = [0.01 - 0.2]$ or $a/h = [5 - 100]$. Two general conclusions can be drawn from Fig.3: (1) the added mass decreases with the wavenumber m , and (2) the added mass decreases with the thickness/length ratio (h/a). For example, for the fluid-plate with free surface shown in Fig.3 (a), $\bar{m}_{add}^* = 2.938, 0.980,$ and 0.294 respectively for $m = n=1, 3,$ and 10 at $h/a = 0.01$. Similar results are obtained for the floating plate shown in Fig.3 (b) because of similar fluid-plate configurations. For the submerged plate shown in Fig.3 (c), $\bar{m}_{add}^* = 5.878, 1.960,$ and 0.588 respectively for $m = n=1, 3,$ and 10 at $h/a = 0.01$.

Figure 3. Non-dimensional added mass $\bar{m}_{add}^* = \frac{m_{add}^*}{\rho_p h}$ for three fluid-plate interaction systems: (a) fluid-plate with free surface, (b) floating plate, (c) submerged plate

5.2 Comparison of vibration frequencies with different models

Fig. 4 shows the natural frequency f as a function of wavenumber $m = n$ for the classical Kirchhoff-Love plate theory and Mindlin plate theory under dry vibration, Fig.4(a), and wet vibration, Fig.4(b), for the case with free fluid surface. The following values are used in the calculations: $E = 200GPa$, $\rho_f = 1025kg/m^3$, $\rho_p = 7850kg/m^3$, $\nu = 0.3$, $a = b = h_1 = 0.8m$, $h = 0.02m$, and $k' = 0.833$. Clearly, the frequency is a linear function of wavenumber for the classical Kirchhoff plate theory in the log-log plot. By contrast, for the Mindlin plate theory, there are two branches of solutions, which are consistent with the two solutions of the quadratic frequency equation, Eq. (31). At low wavenumber values, the higher branch of the frequency solution, Mindlin-H in Fig. 4 (a), is significantly higher than the lower branch, Mindlin-L. As the wavenumber increases, the two branches are getting parallel to each other. It should be noted that the two branches represent the two fundamental vibration mechanisms: longitudinal wave propagation and shear wave propagation. The two asymptotical parallel lines represent these two wave speeds: longitudinal wave speed $c_L = \sqrt{E/\rho_p}$: and shear wave speed $c_s = \sqrt{k'G/\rho_p}$.

Fig.4 (b) shows similar trends for wet vibration at lower wavenumbers ($m < 30$). The curves of higher-branch and higher wavenumbers are more complex and will not be addressed here.

Figure 4. Frequency as a function of wavenumber for (a) dry vibration, (b) wet vibration

Fig. 5 shows the natural frequency f as a function of length/thickness ratio (a/h) and wavenumber $m = n$ for the classical Kirchhoff-Love plate theory and Mindlin plate theory under dry vibration, Fig.5 (a), and wet vibration conditions for the case with fluid free surface, Fig.5 (b). The main results are also listed in Table 2 for comparison. Several key conclusions can be drawn from this study: (1) the frequencies calculated from the Mindlin plate theory are always lower than the corresponding ones obtained from the classical Kirchhoff-Love plate theory because of the effects of rotatory inertia and shear deformation mechanisms. The differences between the results from these two theories are higher for lower a/h ratios. For example, the relative difference is $\delta = (8483.3 - 9597.3)/9597.3 = -12\%$ at $a/h = 5$ and $m = 1$. The difference becomes higher for higher m values but decreases with a/h ratio. (2) The natural frequencies calculated based on the Mindlin plate theory are not always lower than those of the classical Kirchhoff-Love plate theory as observed from Fig.5 (b) and Table 2. In fact, for most of the a/h values studied, the Mindlin plate theory generated frequencies are higher than those generated from the classical plate theory for low wavenumbers such as $m = 1$ and $m = 3$, indicating the complex interaction between the fluid effects and the higher-order deformation mechanisms.

It should be noted that one of the main focuses of this paper is to compare the predicted vibration frequencies from different models, the formulae for dry vibrations are classical and well-established. The formulae for wet vibration are recently new, however, similar results obtained from different research groups have been available for numerical simulations [29-32] as well as analytical analyses [35]. Further comparison and validation work needs to be conducted on orthotropic structures with well-planned comparison and validation matrices.

Figure 5. Frequency as a function of dimension ratio (a/h), wavenumber, and plate models for (a) dry vibration, and (b) wet vibration

Table 2: The values of frequency for different combinations of model, wavenumber, and a/h ratio

a/h	1				3			
	Kirchhoff-Love		Mindlin		Kirchhoff-Love		Mindlin	
	dry	wet	dry	wet	dry	wet	dry	wet
50	95.973	61.078	95.833	61.001	863.756	707.659	852.694	699.246
40	149.958	87.278	149.618	95.246	1349.619	978.837	1322.961	1085.416
25	383.892	223.432	381.678	243.088	3455.025	2505.823	3289.474	2703.868
20	599.831	349.112	594.457	378.765	5398.477	3915.348	5012.563	4126.063
10	2399.323	1396.448	2317.344	1481.193	21593.91	37856.58	17023.09	14096.38
5	9597.292	5585.793	8483.297	5468.411	86375.63	75713.17	47885.83	39719.32

5.3 Uncertainties due to randomness of variables

Since the uncertainty introduced by the fluid is unknown from the literature [41], its contribution will be ignored here. Therefore, only dry vibration based on the classical Kirchhoff-Love plate theory, Eq. (32), with $\bar{m}_{ada}^* = 0$, will be considered for uncertainty and probabilistic analysis in this paper. Box-Muller transform is used to generate four independent sets of standard normally distributed random numbers for Monte Carlo simulation, with each set consisting of 10,000 data points. The corresponding normal and lognormal distribution functions for the relevant parameters are then obtained by using the mean and STD values provided in Table 1 and Eq. (35). The natural frequencies f_{mn} for all combinations of a/h and $m = n$ are calculated and ranked by amplitude. Then, the frequencies at lower 10%, i.e. L_10% and upper 90%, i.e., U_90%, are identified and plotted in Fig. 6 (a) as a function of a/h and $m = n$. The frequency curve based on the nominal values of the relevant parameters are also plotted for comparison. It is clear from Fig.6 (a) that the variations of the predictions due to the parameter uncertainties are noticeable. Fig.6 (b) plotted the relative differences between L_10% and U_90% curves against the nominal curve at $m = n = 1$. It is found that: (1) L_10% and U_90 curves are not symmetrical with respect to the zero-difference curve because of the shifts of the mean values of the parameters listed in Table 1, (2) the relative difference between L_10% and U_90% is near 30%, which is much larger than those observed in the differences caused by the different models, Fig.5 and Table 2. Additionally, the relative difference is relatively stable and insensitive to a/h and $m = n$ values.

Figure 6. The 10% lower and 90% upper bounds of the predicted natural frequencies of the plate in terms of (a) frequency, and (b) relative frequency

6 Conclusions

Fluid-structure interactions are important for the design of naval structures that need to withstand continuous hydrodynamic loading in their lifecycle. Of critical relevance are the vibration characteristics (frequency and mode) of ship panels in contact with sea water on one side and are virtually free on the other side and the structures submerged in sea water. This paper provides a simple analytical framework on dry and wet vibrations of simply supported plates for several different plate theories, with emphasis on uncertainties and variations and their interpretations in ship designs. The deterministic closed-form analytical solutions of added mass and vibration frequencies have derived, some of them for the first time, and the dominating parameters have been identified. Monte-Carlo simulation analysis has been conducted to explore the lower and upper bounds of the analytically obtained vibration frequencies. One of the major observations made from this study is that the uncertainties and variations of the basic parameters can surpass the differences caused by different models, in other words, the uncertainty caused by the randomness of structural parameters is higher than model uncertainty. The proposed deterministic fluid-plate interaction analysis framework and the associated probabilistic uncertainty/variation analysis approach are expected to offer a basis for more advanced fluid-structure interaction research. It is also expected that this research can provide significant insights on how to analytically estimate the added mass and how to validate the boundary element method and other empirical formulae provided in the design codes [2, 3].

Acknowledgment

ZW and PD acknowledge partial support by the Center For Naval Research And Education (CNRE) under ONR Grant N00014-24-1-2023.

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